

SOME ASPECTS OF TEACHING THE GAME OF VOLLEYBALL TO STUDENTS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: The essence, content and features of teaching volleyball to students based on an innovative approach are highlighted in the article.

Key words: technique, tactics, game skills, game discipline, first pace, second pace, "wave", "echelon", "cres", passing the ball, receiving, defense, to 'p into the game, strategy.

Volleyball differs from other sports in its nature, content and characteristics. Modern volleyball is extremely rich in different game skills and tactical combinations, and is played at a great intensity and speed. Therefore, the above-mentioned unique characteristics of volleyball require the players to have perfect technical skills. In competitive games, the more extensive and perfectly formed technical skills are in relation to external influences, the greater the chance of winning.

A game technique is a specialized movement or complex of movements performed simultaneously in a sequence and in a certain purposeful order. The technique of the game should be designed for accurate, fast, light, appropriate, low-effort, high-efficiency execution of the action.

Volleyball game technique consists of a set of movement methods necessary to play the game. Movement technique is evaluated by appropriate, effective movement in various situations. The performance of each technique in the game consists of a system of movements that are connected to each other. Movement techniques are dynamic and kinematic characteristics of movement that are necessary and sufficient for solving movement tasks in a certain way (certain consistency of forces, coordination between certain parts of the body, etc.) [1; p. 8].

The main part of the technique is the most important and decisive part of the main mechanism in a certain movement. Performing the main part of the technique is expressed by the use of a large amount of effort in a relatively short period of time.

The details of the technique are secondary features that do not disturb the main mechanism of movement. Technical details are different for different athletes, which depends on their morphological and functional capabilities.

When performing technical actions, certain phases of actions differ in terms of time. Usually, three phases of actions can be identified: preparatory, main and final phases [2; p. 12].

The importance of the preparatory phase is to create favorable conditions for the performance of the action in the main phase. These conditions are created by running, jumping, turning movements (when blocking, putting the ball in play, when making an attack kick). Actions in the main phase are directly focused on solving the main action tasks. From the point of view of biodynamics, the most important thing in this phase is the effective use of driving forces in the appropriate situation and in the appropriate direction.

Movements in the final phase fade or brake sharply in order to maintain the balance of the body. Since volleyball is a very dynamic game, a volleyball player must master various technical methods, be able to choose them depending on the game situation and perform them quickly and accurately. This determines the technical skills of the player.

Signs of high technical skill are represented by:

- accurate and effective implementation of action methods;
- stability of execution of actions in the presence of external factors (fatigue, negative effects of external conditions);
- choosing response actions depending on the actions of the opponent, reconstructing them and being able to control the parts of the action;
- reliability of execution of methods.

During different periods of volleyball development, the methods, requirements, form, and content of technical movements change and improve. The main reason for the change in technical methods is the change in the rules of the game, the improvement of tactical actions, and the growth of the level of physical fitness of the players. The growth of game dynamics in attack and defense, the increase in the potential of actions, the expansion of the arsenal of

combinations in attack and defense also motivates the renewal or reconstruction of technical methods [3; p. 5].

However, it cannot be said that there are no more effective methods used in the game technique. The functional and physical capabilities of skilled athletes create a perspective for introducing and implementing new, advanced methods of game technique.

Classification of game techniques is to divide them into certain groups and sections based on their form, content, purpose of the used methods, interdependence of actions, kinematic and dynamic structure of actions.

Volleyball techniques are divided into two major sections: offensive and defensive techniques. In turn, the above sections are divided into several groups according to the form and content of technical methods. Each group has its own methods of performing technical actions.

Attack technique.

States, motion, initial states

Situations. In a volleyball game, players must move with the ball in a short time. Therefore, a player needs to be highly prepared to play with the ball in this or that game. For this purpose, it is necessary to occupy different states in order to perform different methods of action.

Figure 1.

When giving an attack shot and making a

block - high (Fig. 1 a), when receiving a ball put into play - medium (Fig. 1 b), an attack shot or a ball that returns below the fence when receiving - low (Fig. 1 v) states are occupied. In this case, the position of the UOM (general center of gravity) depends on the nature of the next movement. It is also worth noting that the height of the player and his coordination ability have a significant impact on UOM. Therefore, the position of effective standing should be such that the UOM can be quickly removed from the support limit and provide the necessary movement and activity [4; p. 11].

Stances are either static (the player does not move) or dynamic (moving the main support from one foot to the other while receiving the ball, making an attack or waiting to block) depending on the nature of the subsequent actions. . In this posture, the hands are at waist level, the fingers are facing the palms, and the body is slightly bent forward. Gavda should be in a free position.

Movement. The player moves around the field to perform a certain technique. Depending on the method and the situation of the game, he performs various actions by stepping (forward, backward, sideways), jumping, running, falling. Stepping and running movements are somewhat soft (due to the slow UOM vibration). Stepping to the side is often used when blocking with a small amount of mass, receiving an offensive shot, or receiving a ball that has changed its direction from the fence. Movement always starts with the foot closest to the

desired direction of movement. It is used in the implementation of quick response actions, such as splashing, jumping, and running. In most cases, the considered actions are also used in the general unit.

Initial conditions. Initial conditions determine the preparatory phase for performing one or another technical method. Acquiring the initial conditions should provide favorable conditions and movement for the expected action. Regardless of the implementation of the technical method, the initial situations differ somewhat statically: before passing the ball (Fig. 2 a), when receiving the ball from below (Fig. 2 b), when blocking (Fig. 2 v- Fig.) and when giving an attack blow (Fig. 2 g).

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Passing the ball is a technical method that creates favorable conditions for the organization and execution of an attack. The ball can be passed: from the base position with two hands, jumping with two hands, jumping with one hand, falling back with two hands. The last method is used in volleyball in rare, tense situations.

Directional passes (relative to the passer) are as follows: forward, over oneself, backward. According to the length: long - more regions; short - from region to region; shortened - within the territory.

By height: high - above 2 meters, medium - up to 2 meters, low - up to 1 meter. Depending on the above indicators, the ball is given slow, fast and high acceleration. The ball can be given close to the net - up to 0.5 meters and far - more than 0.5 meters [5; p. 25].

The technique of passing the ball consists of the initial position, the movement of the hand against the ball, cushioning and the direction of the ball. After moving from the initial position to the ball, the volleyball player is in a vertical position, the degree of bending of the legs depends on the height of the ball's direction and the speed of flight, the palms of the feet are parallel or one foot (opposite to the main hand) is slightly will be ahead. The hands are extended forward, the fingers form an oval shape (Fig. 3).

The hands collide with the ball above the face. In this case, the thumb receives the main load, and the index fingers are the main ones in striking. The middle finger, to a lesser extent, the ring finger and the ring finger, mainly serve to hold the ball from the side. The tension of the muscles of the arms, legs, and body when directing the ball is explained by mutual integrity. In this case, the UOM of the body moves slightly up and forward, and the weight of the body falls on the ends of both legs. The arms are fully straightened at the end of the ball pass.

When organizing complex attack combinations, when the ball is passed high or in order to reduce the flight time of the ball, the jump pass method is used. In this case, the hands are raised slightly above the head and the ball is passed from the high point of the jump due to the active work of the hands.

In the same case, when passing a short ball, the main movement is carried out due to the active work of the fingers (Fig. 4).

When passing the ball backwards (standing with his back to the target), the player gets under the ball. In this case, the back palm of the hand is raised to the back of the head. Passing the ball is performed by bending the arms at the elbows, the body moves back and forth, while the movement is due to the bending of the thoracic and lumbar parts of the spine (Fig. 5). The jump back pass is performed in the same way as the back pass.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

The most difficult way to pass the ball is to pass the ball with one hand by jumping. This method is performed in difficult conditions when the ball lands on the net. In this case, the hand is bent at the elbows and brought forward (Fig. 6). Palms are turned forward, fingers are bent and tensed. The ball transfer is performed due to the flexion of the elbow joint [5; p. 14].

Figure 6.

Throw in the ball. The ball is put into play through this technical method. The main goal of this method is to make the ball as difficult as possible for the opposing team. Therefore, this method is considered a tool of attack technique. Throwing the ball consists of an initial position and three consecutive phases: preparatory (throwing the ball, swinging the hand), main (hitting) and final (hand lowering and subsequent movement) phases.

In volleyball, there are ways to serve the ball from below, from above, from the side above, and from the jump.

In performing these techniques, hitting the ball is performed in a different sequence. First of all, the technique of spinning the ball and then putting the ball without spinning (because it is a bit more complicated) is taught or repeated.

Figure 7.

Low pass. The player leans forward, bends his legs at the knees, and puts one leg forward (opposite to the kicker's hand) (Fig. 7).

The ball is held at waist level with the hand slightly bent at the elbow. The ball is thrown at a distance of 20-30 cm from the body. When striking, the hand is moved back sharply. The kick is performed from the bottom up. The player simultaneously straightens the back leg and shifts the weight of the body to the front leg. After the shot, the hand movement is completed by "following" the ball. The accuracy of hitting the ball from below is determined by three main factors: the direction of the hand swing (zamak) - it should move sharply back; with the height of throwing the ball - it should not be high; hitting the ball - it should be done approximately at waist level.

As a result of the analysis of the conducted scientific and methodical literature and the study of physical education and sports training, it was found that it is necessary to choose and accurately apply teaching methods in the use of new pedagogical technologies used in physical education and sports classes. it was found that there are very few instructions and recommendations.

Training aimed at training volleyball players in technical methods requires extensive use of modern innovative pedagogical technologies, which are one of the main directions of improving students' knowledge, skills and abilities:

References:

1. Ayrapetyans L.R., Pulatov A.A. Voleybol nazariyasi va uslubiyati. Jismoniy tarbiya institutlari va Oliy pedagogika bilim yurtlari uchun darslik. 2011. – 279 b.
2. Ayrapetyans L.R., Godik M.A. Sportivnye igrы. // Monografiya. T.: Ibn Sino, 1991. - 160 s.
3. Ayrapetyans L.R. Voleybol. // Uchebnik dlya vysshix uchebnyx zavedeniy. T.: Zar qalam. 2006. - 240 s.
4. Ayrapetyans L.R., Pulatov A.A., Isroilov Sh.X. Voleybol. // Oliy o'quv yurtlari umumiy kurs talabalari uchun o'quv qo'llanma. T.: 2009. - 77 b.
5. Belyaev A.V. Obuchenie tekhnike igrы v voleybol i yeyo sovershenstvovanie. // Metodicheskoe posobie. M.: Olimpiya. Chelovek, 2008. - 54 s.
6. Berjo. Voleybol vysshego urovnya. // Avtor perevoda s fransuzskogo yazyka Yu.B. Chesnokov. M.: Olimpiya. Chelovek, 2007. - 31 s.